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New breeding techniques
Hybrid breeding
Populations and seed legislation

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‘Sorting the wheat from the chaff’ - Comments on the spelt [:wheat] discussion

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Abstract

The interest in spelt wheat and other so-called ‘ancient grains’ increased significantly in recent years. Compared to einkorn and emmer, however, spelt is not an ‘ancient’ wheat in terms of a cereal founder crop. Moreover, breeding programs in the second half of the 20th century changed the phenotype of spelt wheat from a tall, lodging prone and low input and low yielding crop to a semi-dwarf crop with high yield potential under higher inputs by crosses with common wheat. Since then, there’s a discussion on the ‘purity’ and/or authenticity of spelt among consumers, processors, growers and breeders. In the following, the history of European spelt wheat is outlined, demonstrating that the crop experienced repeatedly gene introgressions from common wheat. Methods claiming to differentiate between pure/traditional and modern varieties based on storage protein patterns are in practice not working for authenticity control. Honoring consumers’ trust in spelt products, irrespective of their motives, it is suggested that breeders stick to typical spelt characteristics during their selection and that processors keep the specific quality traits in spelt products. In turn, marketers are invited not to make false claims related to health issues.

Keywords

Ancient grain · breeding · consumer trust · domestication · hulled wheat · *Triticum aestivum* · *Triticum spelta* · wheat evolution

Introduction

The acreage of spelt wheat (*Triticum spelta* L.) increased significantly in recent years, especially in Central European countries (Grausgruber 2017). The reasons for this increase are manifold. First of all, the consumption of modern wheat varieties was blamed - without scientific evidence - to be responsible for all kinds of adverse health effects by some bestseller books (Brouns *et al.* 2013, Kelly 2015). As a consequence, many consumers turned to a gluten-free diet or to so-called ‘ancient grains’ such as amaranth, quinoa, millets, einkorn, emmer or spelt (WGC 2018), species which have been used to feed the world for thousands of years but were replaced by high yielding cash crops and varieties during the 20th century and were, therefore, never exposed to intensive breeding programmes (Longin & Würschum 2016). Moreover, the increased interest in traditional folk wisdom and medi-

cine rediscovered the medicinal and scientific writings of Hildegard of Bingen (1078-1179), the German Benedictine abbess, who considered spelt wheat to be superior to any other grain in the diet, an optimal food in all forms (bread, porridge, coffee) for all gastrointestinal problems (Strehlow & Hertzka 1988). Today, a wide range of spelt products, from cookies to bread, are available in Central Europe with Hildegard as eponym.

Discussion on ‘pure spelt’

With the increased interest and acreage very soon a discussion on the ‘purity’ of spelt wheat started. Growers and processors of old varieties and/or landraces claimed the legacy of the traditional and pure spelt wheat cultivation for them, blaming modern spelt wheat varieties to be less nutritious and less healthy, and having spelt atypical baking quality due to gene introgressions from common wheat (*T. aestivum*). Brands and production chains were established excluding modern varieties from production, *e.g.* Ur-Dinkel of IG Dinkel (Bärau, Switzerland; www.urdinkel.ch). Most initiatives which grow ‘Ur-dinkel’ today rely on old varieties such as ‘Oberkulmer Rotkorn’, ‘Ostro’, ‘Bauländer Spelz’ or ‘Steiners Roter Tiroler’ or on varieties which were selected from (crosses between) old varieties, *e.g.* ‘Ebners Rotkorn’ or ‘Schwabenkorn’ (Münzing *et al.* 2009) although these varieties are less productive and taller with a tendency to lodging (Longin & Würschum 2014, Galbusera 2015). Moreover, there is no evidence that modern varieties are more “allergic” or less nutritious (Reents & Mück 1999). Various studies were carried out to classify spelt varieties, most of them based on polymorphism in the omega and gamma gliadin pattern (Schober & Kuhn 2003, Wieser 2006, Mayer *et al.* 2012, Koenig *et al.* 2015). However, all these methods failed to identify spelt wheat cultivars which have common wheat in their pedigrees perfectly (Becker *et al.* 2008, Breuer *et al.* 2014, Koenig *et al.* 2015).

History of European spelt wheat cultivation

Spelt remnants were found in many archaeological excavations across Europe from the Late Neolithic to the Iron Age period. In most cases individual specimen were found among other cereals (Körper-Grohne 1989). From archaeological evidence it is assumed that the cultivation of *T. spelta* in Europe started around 2300 B.C. in parts of Switzerland (Akeret 2005). After the Iron Age, the retreat of spelt wheat to marginal areas in Europe started (Körper-Grohne 1989). From the Roman period until the High Medieval period, spelt wheat was the main crop in most parts of Alamannia

(syn. Alemannia, Suebia), the later Duchy of Swabia. Later on, rye (*Secale cereale*) became the dominant grain here, however, spelt wheat remained important, in northern Switzerland still as main crop (Gradmann 1909, Rösch *et al.* 1992, Schilperoord 2013). Spelt remained for long times also a main crop in areas of Asturias (Buxó i Capdevila 1989), southeast Belgium (Billen 1989, Deman 1989, de Moreau de Gerbehaye 1989) and the Carpathian mountains (Markus 1989).

The origin of spelt wheat

For decades, the origin of spelt wheat was supposed to be Alemannia (Gradmann 1909), where the crop evolved between Stone and Bronze Age (Schiemann 1932). Kihara (1944) published the first sound theory regarding the origin of spelt wheat which was confirmed by the artificial synthesis of *T. spelta* by crossing wild emmer (*T. dicoccoides*) with Tausch's goatgrass (*T. tauschii*; syn. *Aegilops squarrosa*) by McFadden & Sears (1945, 1946a,b). Thereafter, Schiemann (1947, 1951) withdrew her first theory and supported the theory that spelt wheat evolved in the regions where *T. dicoccoides*, *T. dicoccum* and *T. tauschii* were naturally present, whereas Bertsch (1949, 1950) continued to claim southwestern Germany as centre of origin of spelt wheat. The findings of *T. spelta* in Iran (Kuckuck & Schiemann 1957) strongly supported southwestern Asia as the area of origination.

It was argued that spelt wheat found his way from Transcaucasia to Eastern Europe and Pannonia, and during the Migration Period with the Suebi to southwestern Germany where the crop was excellently adapted to the prevailing growing conditions (Andrews 1964). Decades later, many research studies on *e.g.* differences in spike disarticulation, allozyme polymorphism (Jaaska 1978), RFLP data (Dvorak & Luo 2001), and variation in the glutenin and gamma gliadin genes (von Buren 2001, Blatter *et al.* 2002, Yan *et al.* 2003, An *et al.* 2005) suggested that European and Asian spelt may be polyphyletic. The separate origins of European and Asian spelt were confirmed by Dvorak *et al.* (2012) studying the allele diversity in the *Tg* (tenacious glume), *Sog* (soft glume), *q* (speltoid spike) and *C* (compact spike) loci. The findings were consistent with suggestions that European spelt derived from a hybridization of hulled emmer with free-threshing hexaploid wheat (Schiemann 1932). The presence of the *C* allele in some European spelt accessions substantiated the hypothesis that at least for some European spelt genotypes the free-threshing hexaploid wheat was club wheat (*T. compactum*). Recently, Novoselskaya-Dragovich *et al.* (2018) confirmed the independent origin of European spelt investigating the polymorphism of LTR retrotransposons in hexaploid wheats.

Spelt wheat breeding in Europe

When the acreage of spelt wheat in Central Europe ceased at the beginning of the 20th century, breeding activities were initiated in Germany and Switzerland to improve the crop. In Baden, Stoll in Meckesheim and Lang in Gaiberg, in Württemberg, the Saatuchtanstalt Hohenheim, Zeiner at the Kgl. Staatsdomäne Neuhaus near Mergentheim and Aldinger at the Steiner'sche Schlossgut Laupheim, and in Bavaria, Fischer in Illertissen and the Fugger'sche Gutsverwaltung in Babenhausen, were involved in spelt wheat improvement (Hillmann 1910, Baur 1920). Almost all breeding stations focused on the selection of elite plants in existing landraces followed by pedigree selection. Thereby, *e.g.* the variety 'Steiner's roter Tiroler Dinkel' was selected from the landrace 'Roter Tiroler' (provenance Höchst, Vorarlberg) which was the most popular

In der beschriebenen Weise habe ich bis jetzt folgende Kreuzungen zwischen Weizen und Spelz mit Erfolg ausgeführt:

Main's standup-Winterweizen	♀	×	brauner Winterkolbenspelz	♂
Square-head-	"	♀	"	♂
"	"	♂	"	♀
Bordier-	"	♀	"	♂
Rivett's bearded (Rauhweizen)	♀	×	"	♂

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Figure 1: Excerpt of Stoll's work on spelt wheat describing the spelt × wheat crosses he carried out to improve grain yield, straw stiffness, rust resistance and ear morphology (Stoll 1902)

variety at that time in Swabia. Seeds of this landrace was regularly imported from Lustenau, Höchst and Bregenz in Vorarlberg across Lake Constance (Baur 1920).

Heinrich Stoll started already in 1894 with spelt wheat breeding and after no success in finding favorable spontaneous mutants, crosses with common wheat were established: 'Heine's Square-head', 'Bordier', 'Main's Standup' and 'Rivett's bearded' were crossed with 'Roter Tiroler' and 'Roter Winterspelz' (Figure 1) (Stoll 1902, Hillmann 1910, Baur 1920). From two crosses, three new varieties were developed (*i.e.* 'Stolls brauner Winterkolbenspelz', 'Stolls weißer Winterkolbenspelz', 'Stolls früher Riesenpelz') (Hillmann 1910). In Hohenheim, two lines (*i.e.* Roter Kolbendinkel Nr. 1, Schlegeldinkel 9a), which were obviously natural hybrids with common wheat, were selected and distributed to other breeding stations for further development and seed multiplication. Moreover, crosses between 'Schlegeldinkel' and 'Squarehead' wheat were carried out in 1904 (Hillmann 1910). Already Körnicke (1885) described in his book on cereal varieties three different spelt varieties (*i.e.* 'Weisser sammetiger Kolbenspelz', 'Weisser sammetiger Grannenspelz' and 'Roter sammetiger Grannenspelz') which were most likely spontaneous hybrids with common wheat. It seems that natural hybridizations between spelt and common wheat appeared not rarely in mixed or nearby crop stands.

In Switzerland, the identification of individual elite plants followed by pedigree selection in Swiss Rotkorn and Weißkorn landraces started in 1908. The work was carried out by farmers under the supervision of the federal seed testing and experimental stations in Oerlikon (Zurich) and Lausanne (Baur 1920, Schilperoord 2013). Selection criteria were *e.g.* plant height, awnedness, thousand grain weight and spike density. After official tests, seeds of the best lines (*e.g.* 'Oberkulm Nr. 3' as Rotkorn and 'Zuzgen Nr. 15' as Weißkorn type) were multiplied and distributed. A second selection cycle and official testing followed end of the 1920s which resulted in the release of further landrace varieties. Due to costs, however, the number of varieties was regionally reduced in the 1930s to two to three varieties each of the Rotkorn and Weißkorn type (Schilperoord 2013).

Despite these first breeding activities, spelt cultivation in Europe nearly disappeared in the second half of the 20th century. In the 1970s, the growing interest in unconventional food and low-input agriculture led to a regional revival of spelt wheat cultivation, especially in marginal areas. To counter the main problem of low productivity and susceptibility to lodging, modern breeding programs established in Belgium, Germany and Switzerland introgressed genes from common wheat to reduce plant height (*i.e.* *Rht* genes) as well as to improve grain yield and technological quality (Kling 1989, 1991, 2009; Winzeler 1989, 1991; Bertin *et al.*

Figure 2: Diversity in spelt wheat genetic resources, varieties and breeding lines with respect to ear morphology and habit, maturity, plant height, yellow rust and lodging resistance, and culm and ear discoloration during ripening (HealthyMinorCereals spelt diversity panel grown at Raasdorf, Austria, 2015 & 2017 - all photos by H. Grausgruber, except bottom right: spelt trial at Jõgeva, Estonia, 2015, by R. Koppel)

2001, Schilperoord 2013). Meanwhile small-scale breeding activities were established in many other European countries which resulted in the release of modern spelt cultivars, some of them originating from crosses with common wheat (e.g. in Poland and Italy) and showing more common wheat specific traits (i.e. high percentage of free-threshing grains, plump and medium long seeds). In Slovakia, 'PS Lubica' was selected from a cross between

common and spelt wheat and registered as common wheat as it is free-threshing but showing technological quality similar to spelt (Hanková et al. 2014). Contrary, 'Emiliano' was registered as free-threshing spelt conservation variety in Germany (Müller 2016).

By April 2018, 61 registered spelt wheat varieties are included in the plant variety database of the European Commission. Among these, seven varieties are registered as conservation varieties.

Most of the varieties originate from Germany, Italy and Switzerland. Further countries with current registrations are Hungary, Austria, Belgium, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Croatia, Czech Republic and The Netherlands. This data illustrates that spelt wheat is today cultivated across Europe, far beyond its 'traditional' growing area in southwestern Germany, Switzerland, western Austria and southeastern Belgium.

The currently available varieties can be grouped roughly in three classes: (i) old landraces and traditional varieties, and (conservation) varieties selected from them with low to medium yield, tall plant height and susceptibility to lodging, but individually high resistance to diseases; (ii) modern varieties with reduced plant height, improved lodging tolerance, medium to very high yield (especially under high-input conditions), but partly spelt atypical characteristics, e.g. higher percentage of free threshing grains, shorter and more plumb seeds; (iii) modern varieties from organic breeding programs with improved lodging tolerance despite relatively tall plant height, medium to high yield (especially under low-input/organic production), and spelt typical characteristics, e.g. long, narrow and sharp-edged grains, culm coloring during ripening (Figure 2).

Conclusions

During its history, European spelt wheat experienced gene introgressions from common wheat several times. Already its origin is based on a natural hybridization between emmer and common wheat. It is also documented that breeding at the end of the 19th century often relied on the selection of offsprings from natural outcrossings between spelt and common wheat, appearing in mixed and/or neighboring crop stands. Hence, it can be assumed that natural hybridizations between wheat (sub)species appeared many a time, especially in mixed crop stands. At the same time, first spelt breeders in Germany started with spelt × common wheat crosses with the aim to improve yield, threshability and lodging resistance. With the introgression of the genes of the Green Revolution in the second half of the 20th century, spelt wheat changed its phenotype significantly from a tall crop, excellently adapted to low-input and adverse growing conditions, to a semi-dwarf crop with high yield potential at mineral fertilization and application of growth regulators.

Consequently, the terminology of 'pure spelt' varieties is not defined but just randomly used for marketing. The use of the gliadin pattern for the classification of spelt wheat varieties does not reflect the percentage of common wheat introgression, but is only the (random) result of selection. Thereby it can be explained why such analyses old and tall varieties (e.g. 'Altgold', 'Steiners roter Tiroler', 'Oberkulmer', 'Ostro') group together with modern, semi-dwarf varieties (e.g. 'Badenkrone', 'Cosmos', 'Spy', 'Zollernspelz') (Koenig *et al.* 2015).

Without doubt, spelt wheat needs, as well as other crops, genetic improvement to cope with changes in growing conditions due to global warming, e.g. new (races of) pathogens, reduced vegetation period, heat stress during grain filling, etc. Therefore, using genes from other wheat (sub)species may be necessary. However, it must be considered that despite the still high interest in 'ancient wheats', the market is highly volatile and sensible. Therefore, breeders have to consider in their selection characteristic spelt traits such as the hulledness, size and shape of the grain, ear morphology, process of ripening with the typical discoloration of the culm, specific taste, chemical composition and product quality.

Many consumers prefer spelt products for whatever the reason. Both processors and breeders have to appreciate the consumers' trust in spelt wheat by providing an authentic product.

Besides common wheat, the diversity present in other spelt gene pools such as the Spanish or Asian, or Georgian spelt (*T. macha*) (Cao *et al.* 1998, Elía *et al.* 2004, Novoselskaya-Dragovich *et al.* 2018) can be used to broaden the genetic basis of European spelt.

Keywords

Ancient grain · breeding history · centre of diversity · domestication · *Triticum spelta* · wheat evolution

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